

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF GRADED FOAM BASED SANDWICH STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO IMPACT

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Abstract

This article describes the low velocity impact response of sandwich structures based on layered cores fabricated by bonding foams with different densities and carbon fiber skins together, investigated both experimentally and numerically. The impact behaviour of the panels was characterized by recording the resulted load-displacement traces and by determining the energy required to perforate the target. The impact response of the graded sandwich structures was modelled using finite element analysis package Abaqus/Explicit. The CFRP skins were modelled as an orthotropic elastic material before failure, and the subsequent damage processes were predicted using Hashin's failure criteria. The PVC foam cores were modelled using crushable foam model with hardening plasticity. The resin at the interface between the CFRP skin and the PVC foam was modelled using the cohesive elements. The predicted load-displacement responses and failure modes are compared with test results, with good agreement.

It has been shown that graded core sandwich structures can out-perform their monolithic counterparts in terms of their impact perforation resistance. It has also been observed that placing higher density foam core against the top surface skin, placing the lowest density foam in the centre of the core and a ductile foam against the lower surface can lead to an improved perforation resistance.

1. Introduction

As a result of their excellent specific properties, composite materials have been extensively used in a growing variety of lightweight structural roles in the

aircraft and automotive industries. Qiao et al [1] provide a brief overview for the research on impact mechanics and high-energy absorbing materials using different theoretical and computational methods. Chai and Zhu have summarized the response of sandwich structures subject to impact loading in his review [2]. Mines et al [3] investigated the low velocity impact response of glass fibre/vinyl ester sandwich panels based on both aluminium honeycomb and Coremat cores. Zhou et al [4] investigated impact response in foam-based sandwich panels using the finite element model. The FE analysis accurately predicted the impact load-displacement responses and the perforation energies of both the plain foams and the sandwich panels.

A number of numerical studies have been undertaken to investigate the impact response of functionally-graded foam sandwich structures. Cui *et al* [5] proposed a functionally-graded foam model to investigate its energy-absorbing characteristics using the finite element method. Etemadi *et al* [6] developed a 3-D finite element model to simulate sandwich panels with functionally-graded cores subjected to low velocity impact loading. The effects of projectile velocity and kinetic energy, as well as the influence of the beam's dimensions on the impact behaviour and associated indentation and displacement histories have been studied using validated models. Avila [7] developed a failure criterion to model piece-wise functionally graded sandwich composites and predicted the failure mode which was obtained in the experimental data successfully. A beam configuration in which the highest density core was located directly below the upper face-sheet, exhibited the most impressive performance. Sburlati [8] presented an elastic bending analysis for circular sandwich panels with

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exponentially-graded material cores which highlighted the advantages of graded cores in decreasing the likelihood of failure. Icardi and Ferero [9] attempted to optimise the performance of sandwich panels with functionally-graded core and faces. The distribution of properties through the thickness (core) and in-plane (face sheets) that minimise the interlaminar stresses at the interface with the core were determined in their study.

This study investigates the impact behaviour of graded foam-based sandwich structures made with carbon fibre resin plastic (CFRP) face sheets and a range of PVC and PEI foam cores. The low velocity impact response is simulated using three dimensional nonlinear finite element models to investigate the influence of core properties and configurations on the perforation resistance of sandwich structures based on a wide range of polymer foams. The impact response of the panels was characterised by recording the resulting load-displacement traces and by determining the energy required to perforate the target. Twelve designs of graded sandwich structures based on three layer foam combinations have been studied.

2. Experimental Work

Sandwich structure with varying core materials through the thickness properties were manufactured by bonding three 10 mm thick foam sheets together and 0.35 mm carbon fiber skins to the surface. Prior to testing, the 0.35 mm thick skins were manufactured by curing two woven CFRE plies in a hot press at 125° C for one hour. The carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (CFRE) skins were bonded to the cores using a two part epoxy resin. Core materials with varying properties through the thickness were manufactured by bonding three layers foam sheets as shown in Figure 1.

Fig1.1. Sketch of configurations of graded foam based sandwich panels

The twelve configurations and average core density of the sandwiches have been tested and summarized in Table 1. The properties of the nine different foams investigated in this study were summarized in Table 2.

Table 1 Foam core configurations of the sandwiches investigated in this study.

Code	Configurations	Average density (kg/m ³)
C1	C100/P80/P60	80.0
C2	P60/P80/C100	80.0
C3	L80/C60/C200	113.3
C4	C200/C60/L80	113.3
C5	C80/L60/C100	76.7
C6	C100/L60/C80	76.7
C7	L60/P60/L140	86.7
C8	L140/P60/L60	86.7
C9	P80/P60/C200	113.3
C10	C200/P60/P80	113.3
C11	C60/L80/L140	93.3
C12	L140/L80/C60	93.3

Table 2 Mechanical properties of three types of foams investigated in this study

	C80	C100	L90	P80
Tensile modulus (MPa)	66	84	50	54
Tensile strength (MPa)	2	2.7	1.4	2.0
Compressive modulus (MPa)	97	125	56	62
Compressive strength (MPa)	1.3	1.9	0.9	1.1
Compressive fracture strain	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
Shear modulus (MPa)	30	38	21	23
Shear strength (MPa)	1.2	1.6	1	1.1
Shear fracture strain	0.23	0.27	0.75	0.23
Density (kg / m ³)	80	100	90	80

Impact testing was conducted on 150 mm square panels using a drop-weight impact tower. The panels were impacted at their centres by a carriage with a 10 mm diameter hemispherical head. The mass of the impactor was 5.56 kg and the release height of the impact carriage was increased up to a maximum of 1.4 metres. The displacement and impact force of the impactor were recorded using a high-speed video camera and a piezoelectric load cell.

3. Finite Element Modelling

Finite element models were developed to simulate the dynamic behaviour of the graded foam based sandwich panels subjected to low velocity projectile impact, which cover all constituent materials.

3.1 Geometrical model and mesh generation

A fully-clamped sandwich panel, based on three layered foam cores, was modelled using ABAQUS/Explicit. The geometry as well as the boundary and loading conditions for the sandwich panel are shown in Figure 1. One half of the panel was modelled since the panel was symmetric. A rigid cylindrical projectile was employed. The initial projectile velocity was set to that based on the perforation energy obtained from the experimental tests. The skin and foam were meshed using continuum shell elements (SC8R) and eight-noded reduced integration elements (C3D8R) respectively.

Fig.1. The geometry, mesh, boundary and loading conditions of the sandwich model.

3.2 Modelling of the CFRP skin

The CFRP face sheet was modelled as an orthotropic elastic material prior to damage initiation. Based on the symmetric nature of the skins, the equivalent elastic modulus values in the longitudinal and transverse directions were assumed. Damage initiation was modelled using Hashin’s failure criteria[10] which assumes four damage initiation mechanisms, namely fibre tension, fibre compression, matrix tension and matrix compression. Using the longitudinal, transverse and shear effective stress tensor components within the plane of the CFRP, the damage initiation criteria can be determined [11]

Fibre tension:

$$F_f^t = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{X_T} \right) + \beta \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{X_L} \right)^2, \hat{\sigma}_{11} \geq 0 \tag{1}$$

Fibre compression:

$$F_f^c = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{X_C} \right)^2, \hat{\sigma}_{11} \leq 0 \tag{2}$$

Matrix tension:

$$F_m^t = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{Y_T} \right) + \beta \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2, \hat{\sigma}_{22} \geq 0 \tag{3}$$

Matrix compression:

$$F_m^c = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{2Y_T} \right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_T} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{Y_C} + \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2 \tag{4}$$

where X_T , X_C are the tensile and compressive strengths in the longitudinal direction, Y_T , Y_C are the tensile and compressive strengths in the transverse direction, S_L , S_T are the longitudinal and transverse shear strengths, and β is a coefficient that specifies the contribution of the shear stress to the fibre tensile initiation criterion. Here β is set to zero, there by assuming that there is no shear stress contribution in the initiation of fibre tensile failure. The damage elastic matrix, which relates the stress and strain and controls degradation of the material stiffness, can be expressed as:

$$C_D = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)/E_1 & (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{21}/E_1 & 0 \\ (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{12}/E_2 & (1-d_m)/E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-d_s)G \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

where G is the shear modulus and D is an overall damage variable, dependent upon the current state of fiber (d_f), matrix (d_m) and shear (d_s) damage, respectively.

Damage evolution is characterised by the negative slope of the equivalent stress-displacement relation after damage initiation has occurred. The fracture energies for the fiber tension G_{ft}^F , fiber compression G_{fc}^F , matrix tension G_{mt}^F and matrix compression G_{mc}^F failure modes are specified to

determine the energy dissipated during damage development.

3.3 Modelling of the PVC foam

Numerical models were developed to simulate dynamic response of foam panels and foam based sandwich panels subjected to projectile impact. This included simulation of the complete perforation failure process of all panels tested. The foam under compression was modelled as a crushable foam material for which the hardening curve was determined from a foam compression test. Deshpande and Fleck [12] proposed a phenomenological yield surface for these closed-cell foams as given by

$$\phi \equiv \frac{1}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{3}\right)^2\right]} \left[q^2 + \alpha^2 \sigma_m^2 \right] - \sigma_y^2 \leq 0 \quad (6)$$

where σ_y is the uniaxial tensile or compressive yield strength of the foam, q is the Von Mises stress, σ_m is the mean stress. In Eq. (1), α defines the shape of the yield surface [13], which is related to the ratios of the initial uniaxial yield stress (σ_c^o) and the hydrostatic tensile yield stress (p_t) to the hydrostatic compressive yield stress (p_c^o), respectively. The yield stress (p_c) in hydrostatic compression provides the evolution of the yield surface size and can be expressed as:

$$p_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) = \frac{\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) \left[\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^2} + \frac{1}{9} \right) + \frac{p_t}{3} \right]}{p_t + \frac{\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol})}{3}} \quad (7)$$

where ε_{pl}^{vol} is the plastic volumetric strain for the volumetric hardening model, which is equal to ε_{pl}^{axial} , uniaxial compressive plastic strain. Therefore, p_c should be determined from a uniaxial compression test on the foam.

3.3 Modelling of the resin layer and other contact conditions

Cohesive elements [14] were used to model the resin layers between the composite skins and the cores. The maximum nominal stress and the effective

displacement following a linear softening law were introduced to simulate the mechanisms of damage initiation and progression respectively.

Damage initiation in the cohesive elements was controlled by the ratios of the predicted nominal stress components, based on elastic traction-separation behaviour, to the corresponding critical values in tension (debonding) or shear (sliding) at the interface, which can be expressed as:

$$\max \left\{ \frac{t_n}{t_n^0}, \frac{t_s}{t_s^0}, \frac{t_t}{t_t^0} \right\} = 1 \quad (7)$$

where t_n , t_s and t_t are the stress components predicted by the elastic traction-separation behaviour for the current strain without damage and t_n^0 , t_s^0 and t_t^0 are the corresponding critical values of the nominal stress.

Damage evolution is based on the effective displacement with the linear softening law, which is defined as [15],

$$D_{coh} = \frac{\delta_m^f (\delta_m^{\max} - \delta_m^0)}{\delta_m^{\max} (\delta_m^f - \delta_m^0)} \quad (8)$$

where δ_m^f the effective displacement at complete failure, δ_m^0 relative to the effective displacement at damage initiation, δ_m^{\max} refers to the maximum value of the effective displacement attained during the loading history.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Load-displacement Responses

Low velocity impact tests were undertaken on the twelve core configurations outlined in Table 1. A typical load-displacement trace for a sandwich panel based on the C80/L60/C90 foam combination shown in Fig. 3. Agreement between the FE predictions and the experimental data is very good, with the model captures all of the major features of the experimental trace, including the pronounced second peak associated with the crushing of the core against the distal skin. The graded foam based sandwich structures with similar lower density foams exhibit a classic load-displacement trace, with pronounced

peaks associated with fracture of the front and rear skins and a relatively smooth plateau resulting from the projectile passing through the foam cores with similar densities. An examination of the figure indicates that the force initially increased up to approximately 763 Newtons at which point it reaches a plateau. The force then remains roughly constant as the projectile perforates the three foam materials, suggesting that the fracture properties of the three foams are similar. Finally, the force begins to increase rapidly as the projectile approaches the rear surface of the target. Here, it is likely that the lowermost foam is crushed between the steel impactor and the rear surface skin. Clearly, the peak force associated with fracture of the rear skin is approximate two times higher than that needed to cause failure in the top skin. Finally, the force drops rapidly at a displacement of 38 mm as the projectile fully perforates the lower skin and passes through the composite. Figure 3b shows cross-sections of the fully perforated sandwich structures, where the presence of a distinct cylindrically-shaped shear zone is evident in both the test specimen and the model.

Fig. 3. Load-displacement traces and resulting cross-sections for (a, b) the C80/L60/C90 and (c, d) for the C90/L60/C80 sandwich structure
 Figure 3c shows the measured and predicted load-displacement traces for the equivalent inverted

structure, i.e. the C90/L60/C80 core configuration. An examination of the figure suggests that there are many similarities with its counterpart in Figure 3a. Closer inspection highlights the presence of the three cores, with the plateau loads resistance from approximately 500 to 450 to 600 Newtons as the projectile passes through the three foams. The experimental trace also exhibits a more pronounced initial peak and a larger exit peak. The corresponding cross-sections are shown in Figure 3d, where a cylindrically-shaped perforation zone is again present. Closer inspection of the lowermost foam highlights the presence of a frustrum-shaped zone similar to that observed following impact tests on plain foams [16]. Cone-shaped fracture zones, such as this, are associated with a combined tensile/shear mode of failure, rather than the pure shear mode occurring during the earlier stages of the perforation process. Once again, agreement between the predicted and measured load-displacement curves is generally good, although the model fails to identify the brittle failure mode in the top skin.

Fig.4. Load-displacement traces and resulting cross-sections for (a, b) the P80/P60/C200 and (c, d) for the C200/P60/P80 sandwich structure

Fig. 4a shows the experimental and numerical load-displacement traces for the P80/P60/C200 sandwich structure. The experimental trace exhibits a number of distinct regions as the projectile passes through the various components of the sandwich panel. The initial portion of the trace is linear up to approximately 697 Newtons, at which point the top surface skin fractures and the load drops. The force then oscillates around a value of approximately 490 Newtons, as the projectile passes through the tough P60 foam. The force then reduces as the impactor passes through the more brittle crosslinked foam (P60) before increasing rapidly as it encounters the C200 foam. The final stage of the load-displacement trace exhibits a region in which the force oscillates as the C200 foam is crushed and densifies under the constraint applied by the rear surface skin. The FE prediction of second peak load is lower than the experimental one, which is likely due to underestimated the hardening behaviour on the bottom foam layer. In spite of these discrepancies, agreement between the numerical and experimental data is reasonably good. Figure 4b shows that the perforation zone is again cylindrically-shaped, although a small cone crack is in evidence at the exit surface.

The load-displacement traces for the corresponding inverted sandwich structure (C200/P60/P80) are shown in Figure 4c. Here, the different fracture responses of the three foams are apparent, with the uppermost, high density C200 foam offering the greatest resistance to perforation and the more brittle P60 system exhibiting the lowest. It is also interesting to note that the force associated with fracturing the lowest skin is less than that apparent in Figure 4a, due to the lower densification characteristics of the P80 foam. The resulting cross-section from the test, Figure 4d, highlights the presence of a crack in the uppermost C200 foam that appears to have influenced the subsequent failure locus in the remainder of the structure. This mixed form of failure has been partly captured by the FE model.

Figure 5a shows the force-displacement traces for the C60/L80/L140 sandwich structure, in which the low density cross-linked foam is placed at front and high density linear foams placed at medial and rear layers. Here, the predicted initial peak load is 593 N which is 12% lower than the test one of 670.5 N. The steep increase on the resistant force after the

first peak as well as the second peak load are well simulated by the FE modeling. Clearly, there are similarities between this response and that shown in Figure 4a, with the perforation force increasing in three steps between the peaks associated with fracturing the upper and lower skins. The plateau force resulting from fracturing the tough L140 foam is significantly higher than that required to perforate its lower density C60 counterpart.

Fig. 5. Load-displacement traces and resulting cross-sections for (a, b) the C60/L80/L140 sandwich structure and (a, b) for the L140/L80/C600 sandwich structure

Finally, the load-displacement response of its inverted counterpart is shown in Figure 5c. The comparison clearly highlights the success of the model in predicting the perforation resistance of the foams with various densities. The resistance exhibits an higher initial peak and second peak resulting from fracture of the front skin supported by a high density liner foam of L140. Then the resistance force is in a drop trend at a displacement of 28mm, associated the perforation of the medial and rear foams. The perforation resistance of these foams increases with the increase of equivalent density of the foam accordingly. Once again, agreement between the experimental data and the model is very good, suggesting that the FE analysis is capable of

capturing the fundamental response of these multi-layered structures.

4.2 Perforation Energies of the Sandwich Panels

Fig. 6 Comparison of the predicted and experimental perforation energies.

Figure 6 plots energy absorptions of graded foam based sandwich panels modelled against those obtained from the corresponding experimental measurements. The energy required to perforate the sandwich panels was calculated by determining the area under the load-displacement traces. The perforation resistance of these foams increases with the increase of equivalent density of the foam accordingly. The differences between the simulated and experimental results are within 10%, except for the C4 with 14.2 % higher and C8 with 12.3% lower than the corresponding test ones.

The comparison clearly highlights the success of the model in predicting the perforation resistance of the foams with various configurations, with error below fourteen percent. The figure also shown that the perforation energy varies quite significantly, with the experimental values passing from 21.9 Joules for the C100/L60/C80 sandwich to 40.8 Joules for the C200/P60/P80 configuration. Within each density grouping of structures, there are distinct variations that depend on the specific arrangement of the layers. This is most evident in Panels C9 (P80/P60/C200) and C10 (C200/P60/P80) in which the former has the high density C200 core at the uppermost surface and latter at the bottom surface. Placing the higher density, tougher foam uppermost resulted in a 30% increase in the perforation resistance. An examination of the failure

mechanisms of Structure C9 highlighted the presence of a distinct cone-shaped crack in the lower C200 foam. This can be explained from the cross-sections that this form of failure is associated with a mixed mode of loading (Mode I /Mode II) and also the fact that the Mode I work of fracture is much lower than its Mode II value.

A typical load-displacement trace for a sandwich panel based on the single type plain foam has been predicted by developed FE model [4]. For example, a C130/C130/C130 construction, the perforation resistance of single type core based sandwich structures are compared with of the graded foam cores. Figure 7 shows prediction of sandwiches with Cross-linked plain foam includes foam density from 60 to 200 kg/m³. The FE model captures all of the major features of the impact load in plain foam based sandwiches, including the pronounced first and second peak associated with perforated the top skins and the crushing of the core against the distal skin. The single type foam based sandwich structures exhibit a classic load-displacement trace as earlier test results, with pronounced peaks associated with fracture of the front and rear skins and a relatively smooth plateau resulting from the projectile passing through the foam cores with single type core layer. The resistance force increased from 310 to 1350 N approximately with the increasing of core density of foam layer from 60 to 200 kg/m³.

Fig. 7.FE prediction of load-displacement traces for the sandwich with single type foam core

The energy absorption of the single type foam based sandwiches have been calculated based on the predicted load displacements traces to compare with

the graded foam based sandwiches. Figure 8 plots the energy absorption of sandwich with single cross-linked foam based sandwich and a increase trend has shown in the chart. Compare with the energy absorption of graded foam based sandwiches, the energy absorption of single type foam core based sandwich lower than the graded foam counterpart, which suggested that graded structures can out-perform their monolithic counterparts in terms of their perforation resistance.

Fig. 8 Comparison of perforation energy against the average core density between different structures

Figure. 8 shows plot of the perforation energy versus average target density for the graded foam based sandwiches as well, highlight the benefit of placing the highest density foam on the top surface. An examination of the figure indicates that those laminates in which the highest density foam is placed uppermost tend to out-perform equivalent inverted systems. It also evident that graded structures can out-perform their monolithic counterparts in terms of their perforation resistance. The figure also suggests that this enhancement tends to increase with increasing average foam density.

4.3 Cost performance of the sandwiches

Cost is also an important parameter in the design process although performance is a key criterion in selecting a particular core for a given sandwich structure. Here, a cost factor was determined by normalising the cost of each foam by the cost of the most expensive foam P80 and then by multiplying this value by 100. The relative performance of each

graded foam was then compared on a cost basis by dividing the perforation energy values by the cost factor, and these results are presented in Figure 9 An examination of cost performance indicates that the perforation energy/cost ratio varies significantly across the range of structures considered. Structure C5 based largely on low-density foams. The performance of this sandwich structure out-performs Structures C1 and C2 by a factor of approximately four. C10 has lower cost performance although the perforation energy is the highest. It’s interesting to note that the C3 and C4 have both higher energy absorption and cost performance.

Fig. 9 Cost performance of graded foam based sandwiches

5. Conclusions

The low velocity impact response of sandwich structures based on layered cores has been studied both experimentally and numerically. The numerical model predicted the associated load-displacement traces and the corresponding perforation energies with a high degree of accuracy. It has been evidenced that graded structures can out-perform their monolithic counterparts in terms of their perforation resistance. It has been noted that placing the high density foam core against the top surface skin can lead to an improved perforation resistance compare to sandwich panels with the higher density foam in contact with the rear surface. Secondary benefits associated with placing the lowest density foam in the centre of the core and a ductile foam against the lower surface have also been observed. Finally, significant differences are observed between

the various sandwich configurations when the unit cost of the various foams is considered.

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